

Evaluating Living Labs' role in policy domain

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Abstract

Addressing complex societal challenges through public policy increasingly demands a holistic perspective that integrates sectoral and interdisciplinary knowledge in the science-policy-and-society interface. In this context, Living Labs (LLs) have emerged as a policy tool, a research infrastructure and a governance mechanism in the policy domain. Despite their growing relevance, the role of Living Labs within the broader policy landscape remains underexplored. This study aims, first, to analyse how existing LL literature aligns with various stages of the policy cycle. Second, it evaluates selected LL case studies using a combined Theory of Change and Learning Framework to assess the types of evidence generated, as well as the outcomes and policy impacts of their activities. Preliminary findings suggest that Living Labs are most commonly linked to the agenda-setting and policy implementation phases. Additionally, the case study of the KLIMAP Living Lab illustrates its contribution to both tangible outcomes and broader impacts within policy domain.

Key words

Living labs, Policymaking, policy stages, evaluation, impacts

Introduction

Over the past two decades, living labs have emerged as dynamic, collaborative environments that bring together actors from public and private sectors, academia, and civil society to promote open and user-centered innovation (Bhatta et al., 2023; Hossain et al., 2019; Schuurman et al., 2015). More recently, they have also been recognized as strategic tools for enhancing public policy and governance (Nesti, 2017; Veeckman & Temmerman, 2021). Living labs can support policymaking in multiple ways: (i) by producing actionable evidence and public value through real-world exploration and experimentation (Hansen & Fuglsang, 2020), (ii) by acting as boundary spanner that facilitates engagement across the quadruple helix of stakeholders (Choudhury et al., 2023), thereby subsiding the obstacles of having scarce actor interactions that impede the translation of evidence into policy action (Smith & Kawachi, 2020), (iii) by enabling the feedback loop required to support policy actions with their flexible and iterative approaches (Bhatta et al., 2023; Leutert, 2021).

In the policymaking process, while policy officials hold the decision-making authority, non-state actors often play a supportive role by providing evidence that can inform the policymaking process (EGU, 2025). Evidence-based policymaking rests on the principle that decisions should be guided by the best available knowledge to improve policy outcomes (Eden & Wagstaff, 2021). However, evidence should be understood not as purely objective data, but as knowledge co-produced through the mobilization of resources, integration of diverse knowledge, and value-based processes (De Marchi et al., 2016). In this context, living labs offer a unique opportunity to align innovation with policy needs, generating context-relevant evidence that can inform decision-making. However, despite being aptly positioned as a collaborative, iterative, and evidence-based tool to support policymaking and governance, the role of living labs in supporting policy development and implementation through evidence remains significantly underexplored.

The goal of this study is two-fold. First, we aim to investigate the positioning of living labs within the policy cycle, exploring their function as instruments for knowledge production and innovation in support of evidence-based policymaking. To this end, it examines how existing living labs have contributed to different stages of the policy cycle. However, being aligned to a certain stage doesn't mean that intended outcomes were achieved, thus living labs must undergo monitoring and evaluation to assess how their design, input, and processes have resulted intended output, outcomes, and (policy) impact

(Eden & Wagstaff, 2021). Accordingly, this paper employs a theory-driven approach to policy evaluation by developing a ‘Theory of Change’ (ToC) (Guarneros-Meza et al., 2018) in combination with the living lab learning framework (Bhatta et al., 2025), to assess the role of living labs in informing, assisting, and enhancing evidence in the policymaking. Consequently, we aim to explore how living labs can effectively be positioned as a ‘knowledge and innovation’ tool to support evidence-based policymaking.

Brief theoretical background

Positioning of LL in policy stages

Public policies are complex objects designed to achieve defined goals and solutions to societal problems (Knill & Tosun, 2008). The policymaking process is non-linear, iterative and highly contingent. However, conceptualized as sequential parts or stages, the policy stages help organize the complex and seemingly chaotic dynamics of policymaking (Capano & Pritoni, 2020; De Marchi et al., 2016; Sutcliffe, 2005). It analytically divides the policy process into distinct stages, enabling a better grasp of the specific dynamics occurring within each stage. In this study, we take the six stages of the policy cycle, namely, agenda-setting, policy formulation, adoption, implementation, evaluation, and support (Donkoh et al., 2023; EGU, 2025). Figure 1 shows these stages while highlighting their non-linear and iterative nature in practice.

Figure 1. Stages of the policy cycle and possible points of influence of evidence at each stage

Evidence-based policymaking is integrated into the policy cycle when decisions need to be informed by reliable data, research and analysis, promoting better outcomes and

accountability. We aim to explore living labs as evidence-generating tools along the lines of single stages. about what constituents evidence, it includes scientific research (such as research, surveys, statistical data, qualitative analysis and so on) as well as other forms of evidence (such as, economic, behavioural, anecdotal, etc.), history, local knowledge and culture (Campbell et al., 2007; Strydom et al., 2010). Living labs are well-suited to incorporate such evidence into the policy-making process for each stage, as shown in Table 1 and Figure 2.

Table 1. Role of living labs in building evidence for each stage of the policy cycle (expanded)

Policy stages	Potential role of LLs
Agenda setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • by playing the role of ‘policy advocate’ by bringing the state’s attention by collaboratively identifying and prioritizing issues needing attention through exploration and experimentation by generating evidence that can be foundational for forming new policies and anticipating policy relevant emerging issues (EGU, 2025).
Formulation and Adoption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • by providing policymakers justified grounds for selecting certain measures, based on the evidence produced by co-creation in LL (although policy adoption isn’t rational) • Policy experimentation to generate evidence for informed policymaking by providing legitimacy by involving multiple stakeholders, this can occur at different levels, i.e., local or national, based on the scale of the living lab.
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By generating evidence to inform best practices for executing policies through real-time data collection and feedback loops help adjust strategies for better outcomes • Engaging diverse stakeholder for implementing policy interventions • Piloting policies; policy experimentation
Monitoring and Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • by evaluating the effectiveness of a certain policy through data-driven, user-centric assessments to determine whether a policy achieved its goals or requires modification.
Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • by collaborating with relevant stakeholders to help identify policies that require modification and determine how the existing policy intervention can be expanded/scaled or assess which polices should be discontinued.

Figure 2. Role of living labs in building evidence for each stage of the policy cycle

Evaluation of living labs

There is a growing emphasis on incorporating both longitudinal and point-in-time evaluations within living labs. Evaluation is a core management instrument and part of many research and innovation projects (Schaefer et al., 2021). Theory of change (ToC) is one of such widely used evaluation framework that can be employed for any level of intervention, ranging from an event, a project, an organization, a policy, or even separately for each stage of the policy cycle. ToC seeks to understand the context, to identify the specific goals of the program, assumptions, and preconditions, and to connect those goals to particular interventions (Dekker et al., 2021; Rengarajan & Sivasubramaniyan, 2020; Taplin & Clark, 2012). Thus, it explains how activities lead to a series of results that contribute to achieving intended impacts. ToC informs evidence-based policymaking by revealing place-based challenges, proposing solutions, demonstrating outcomes and also providing reasons for their success or failure (Dekker et al., 2021; Reed et al., 2023). Living lab and its stakeholder partnership is almost like a strategic alliance that is highly evolutionary and goes through a sequence of interactive cycles of learning, re-evaluation, and readjustment (Doz, 1996). Thus, we combine the ToC with a living lab learning

framework (Bhatta et al., 2025), that highlights content, capacity, and network learning types during the co-creation activities and links to its results.

Here, content learning includes sharing diverse insights to create a new or comprehensive understanding directed towards the immediate result, i.e., the development of the desired intervention, and can be logically linked to innovative output. Capacity learning type is acquiring and enhancing the ability to learn and adopt new knowledge & skills and can be linked medium-term consequences. Similarly, network learning deals within the network of actors as well as a network of several living labs with common goals to better distribute, iterate, and upscale the knowledge, ultimately reaching a wider community and generating a longer-term impact. However, it is important to note that all learning types are interconnected with each other and are directly or indirectly connected to the output, outcomes, and impact. Content, capacity, and network learning during co-creation activities can be combined with ToC to better connect the activities that are undertaken with the output, outcome, and impact through learning, as visualized in Figure 3. In this paper, we apply this framework with the intention of understanding the policy impacts of the LL case studies.

Figure 3. A combined framework for living lab evaluation

Method

The research follows multiple methods. First, a literature review is being conducted using relevant keywords to understand the position of living labs within the policy cycle (A). Next, five living lab case studies are selected, and semi-structured interviews (3 per LL) are conducted with the coordinators, project leaders, and experts involved in those LLs (B). Five living labs selected are KLIMAP (KLIMAP, 2020-2024), Working with water and landscapes (Werken met Waterlandschappen, 2022), Self-supporting river systems (Self-

supporting river system, 2022), Living lab Schouwen Duiveland, and Soil-Health Living Labs (SOILLStartup, 2024). All five living labs contain policy elements, are located within Europe and aim for sustainable soil, land and water management. Questions were asked to understand the design, activities related to knowledge development, capacity building and networks, their position in the policy cycle and expected/ achieved policy outcomes and applied to the framework in Figure 3. So far, we only have presentable results from KLIMAP LL.

Figure 4. Strategy adopted in this study

Preliminary result

Positioning of LL in policy stages

Our ongoing review shows that living labs are primarily aligned with the agenda-setting and policy implementation stages (as shown in Figure 5).

Figure 5. Analysis of LL alignment with each policy stage

Evaluation of KLIMPA LL

KLIMAP adopts real-world co-creative approaches to generate knowledge on climate-resilient land and water adaptation in the Dutch sandy soil region. Its goal was to investigate measures to retain and store water to combat extreme precipitation and prolonged periods of drought, especially in the higher sandy soil region. It is positioned within the agenda-setting stage of the policy cycle. Its *output* lies in generating new integrated knowledge and hard evidence regarding alternatives for climate adaptive measures for sandy soils. These results are to help municipalities and provinces select measures in their regional area. Its *outcome* lies in building capacity among public body personnel to use innovative tools such as development pathways in selecting these measures. There is a strong emphasis on the improvement of the civil service department’s capacity to make the best use of evidence (Treasury, 2007), which was, to a certain degree achieved, by KLIMAP. Finally, together with numerous other similar living labs and co-creative projects, its impact is on broad policy guideline “water-soil steering”, by the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water.

Figure 6. KLIMAP's result, outcome and impact (in brief)

Conclusion

As research-in-progress, many elements mentioned in this paper require further nuanced discussion, which is currently absent. However, we can conclude that living labs are increasingly being aligned and positioned within one or more policy stages, particularly during the agenda-setting and implementation stage. Indeed, living lab's contribution to policymaking is not only limited to providing evidence, but they also drive innovation, create transparency, legitimacy, and accountability, embrace inclusivity, and support decision-making through feedback loops and iterative learning. Despite these contributions, the extent to which these labs achieve the intended policy outcomes remains largely undocumented. To this end, evaluation of living labs can help identify living lab outcomes and intended/ achieved policy impacts. Since no standardized evaluation framework for living labs exists, the application of a combined ToC and learning framework to the KLIMAP LL reveals that the outputs and outcomes of living labs correspond to their level of operation. Further, a broader network of LLs with similar objectives could potentially lead to a more extensive policy impact. However, a single LL isn't sufficient to draw definitive conclusions at this point. Upon completion, we aim to identify in what ways/ capacities and to what degree are LLs able to contribute to policy processes.

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